

Active Learning for Uncertainty Quantification of a Physics-Informed Digital Twin of a Thermal Energy Distribution System

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ABSTRACT

Complex hybrid energy systems such as Idaho National Laboratory's Thermal Energy Distribution System (TEDS) require controllers that rely on fast, interpretable, and uncertainty-aware surrogates rather than on slow high-fidelity models. We investigated application of Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics with Control (SINDyC) and its probabilistic extension, Multivariate-Gaussian SINDyC (MvG-SINDyC), to yield a robust, uncertainty-aware surrogate for the TEDS digital twin. We then built a probabilistic surrogate by fitting MvG-SINDyC to the TEDS data. To avoid exhaustive training, we wrapped the model in an active-learning (AL) loop. Starting from a small training set, we (i) fit MvG-SINDyC, (ii) performed an accuracy and 95% coverage assessment on the experimental trajectory, and (iii) selected the next batch of simulations that most improved agreement with the experiment in the model coefficient space. This focused the computation on where it had the largest impact, while also keeping the surrogate transparent and fast. For TEDS, the AL-driven surrogate reduces error more quickly and reaches stable performance earlier than does random selection across multiple training-pool sizes for two outputs: the glycol heat exchanger (GHX) bypass mass flow rate (\dot{m}) and heat rate Q . Gains are strongest in the low-data regime, where AL is able to reach a similar error-coverage trade-off with about an order of magnitude fewer models (roughly ~ 60 vs. ~ 480). The learning curves also reveal clear diminishing returns, suggesting a practical early stopping criterion. Overall, this study provides a simple, data-efficient path to an uncertainty-calibrated, interpretable surrogate that is suitable for supervisory control and reduces reliance on exhaustive simulation, thus supporting faster, more robust digital twin deployment for integrated energy systems (IES).

Keywords: Digital Twin, Thermal Energy Distribution System (TEDS), Multivariate Gaussian SINDyC (MvG-SINDyC), Active Learning, Uncertainty Quantification

1. INTRODUCTION

The Thermal Energy Distribution System (TEDS), located in the Dynamic Energy Transport and Integration Laboratory at Idaho National Laboratory (INL), serves as a testbed for exploring hybrid energy systems that co-generate electricity and non-electric products [1]. Traditionally, individual TEDS components are managed using decoupled proportional-integral controllers. However, this decentralized approach fails to account for the tightly coupled interactions and physical constraints of the system. To overcome this limitation, researchers are actively developing supervisory controllers capable of integrating multicomponent signals and optimizing system-wide performance [2]. These controllers aim to increase operational efficiency and economic value, theoretically enabling faster and more reliable control actions in comparison to manual interventions [3]. Among the most promising advanced strategies is model predictive control (MPC), a control framework that explicitly incorporates system dynamics

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and constraints into its optimization process [4]. MPC computes a sequence of future control actions by solving a constrained optimization problem over a prediction horizon, using a dynamic model of the system. At each time step, only the first control input is applied before re-optimizing based on new measurements, thus enabling adaptive, real-time control under uncertainty. This predictive capability makes MPC particularly well-suited for complex, multi-input/multi-output systems such as TEDS [5].

To support control strategy development, a physics-based model of TEDS was developed in Modelica/Dymola during the system's pre-experimental phase [6]. Although the model is efficient for off-line simulation, its direct use within real-time supervisory controllers (e.g., MPC) is impractical due to solver latency, variable-step integration, and repeated model-evaluation requirements. MPC generates optimal control actions by forecasting how system state variables evolve in response to exogenous disturbances such as grid demand fluctuations or weather variability. For MPC to be effective, the underlying system model must be fast, accurate, interpretable, and differentiable. These requirements have led to the adoption of surrogate modeling approaches that approximate system dynamics over relevant operating envelopes, based on data generated from simulations.

Rather than repeatedly solving differential-algebraic equations during each control cycle, surrogate models are trained to map only the input-output relationships relevant to the controller. This reduces the system's dimensionality and enables orders-of-magnitude faster computations. Of the various surrogate modeling approaches, Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics with Control (SINDyC) has gained particular traction due to its simplicity, interpretability, and performance—even in highly nonlinear systems [7, 8, 9]. SINDyC identifies governing equations in explicit analytical form, facilitating physical interpretation and seamless integration with optimization solvers. Furthermore, its differentiability enhances gradient-based optimization within the MPC loop. To enable reliable and autonomous control of complex systems such as TEDS, digital twins must not only be fast and interpretable, but also able to quantify their own uncertainty. Uncertainty quantification is essential for ensuring that control decisions remain robust even in the presence of model mismatch, sensor noise, or unexpected transients. In prior work, the authors proposed a probabilistic extension to SINDyC—namely, the Multivariate Gaussian Fit SINDyC (MvG-SINDyC)—in which uncertainties were obtained by training ensembles of SINDyC models and fitting a multivariate Gaussian over the resulting coefficient distributions. This approach differs from classical ensemble-based methods by modeling correlations among coefficients directly, yielding a single compact probabilistic surrogate [5]. However, to train SINDyC models, trajectories were chosen via random sampling, a common baseline that is straightforward to implement but agnostic to information content.

This study builds on the MvG-SINDyC framework so as to advance data-efficient surrogate modeling for autonomous control of integrated energy systems (IES). Instead of using random or exhaustive sampling, we introduce an active learning (AL) strategy that selects the most informative simulation trajectories [10]. Specifically, we use the Mahalanobis distance in the model coefficient space to identify simulations that are most similar to experimental behavior, taking into account both scale and correlation. Mahalanobis distance measures how far away a point is from a distribution's mean, accounting for variance and correlations between features [11]. This targeted sampling accelerates convergence to accurate, uncertainty-calibrated surrogates, using fewer simulations. As a result, it supports scalable real-time deployment of digital twins in IES without sacrificing robustness or interpretability.

The remaining sections of this paper are organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the TEDS facility and the design of the simulation and experimental trajectories. Section 3 reviews SINDyC, and introduces the MvG-SINDyC formulation and AL query design. Section 4 presents results comparing random vs. AL selection. And Section 5 discusses implications for AL-enabled modeling and outlines areas of future work.

2. EXPERIMENT AND SIMULATION DATA COLLECTION

2.1. TEDS

TEDS is comprised of a 200 kW heater, a single-tank packed-bed thermal energy storage (TES) system, and a glycol heat exchanger (GHX), along with associated piping, five valves, and temperature/flow sensors. The experiment cycles through startup (warm-up), charging, standby, discharging, and cooldown [6]. For modeling and control, the TES state vector includes inlet mass flow $\dot{m}_{tes,in}$, outlet temperature $T_{tes,out}$, and three node temperatures T_{top} , T_{mid} , T_{bot} ; and the GHX state includes bypass flow $\dot{m}_{ghx,bypass}$ and heat rate Q_{ghx} . Actuation is effected by the valve position PV_{006} , pump outlet flow $\dot{m}_{pump,out}$, inlet loop temperature $T_{pump,in}$, and heater outlet temperature $T_{heater,out}$. These inputs drive the coupled TES-GHX dynamics studied herein. In this study, we analyzed the GHX state $\dot{m}_{ghx,bypass}$ and Q_{ghx} for discharge window ($\approx 9,180$ – $14,640$ s).

2.2. Modelica

We used Modelica/Dymola model of TEDS to generate synthetic trajectories because only one experimental trajectory was available per quantities of interest. Actuator ranges were expanded around the experimental setpoints, and 500 candidate time series were drawn via Sobol sequence sampling (Fig. 1). All signals were refined to a common length of 5,251 points over a duration of 5,460 s. We formed four training pools (4, 8, 12, and 16 trajectories per model), and for each we pre-fit 500 SINDyC models from randomly drawn combinations. These SINDyC models were then queried via the AL procedure.

Figure 1. Experimental (blue line) and Modelica (black lines) actuators and GHX states.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics with Control (SINDyC)

We modeled the TEDS dynamics with SINDyC, which learns system governing equations from time-series data via sparse regression. For the present work, we restricted the candidate library to linear terms such that the identified surrogate was linear state space, thus easing interpretation and control integration. With measured states \mathbf{x} and inputs \mathbf{u} , SINDyC estimates coefficient matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} from data. For TEDS, the TES and GHX surrogates took the following form:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{TES}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{TES}}\mathbf{x}_{\text{TES}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{TES}}\mathbf{u}_{\text{TES}} + \mathbf{d}_{\text{TES}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_{\text{GHX}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{GHX}}\mathbf{x}_{\text{GHX}} + \mathbf{B}_{\text{GHX}}\mathbf{u}_{\text{GHX}} + \mathbf{d}_{\text{GHX}}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{TES}} = [\dot{m}_{\text{TES}}, T_{\text{TES,out}}, T_{\text{top}}, T_{\text{mid}}, T_{\text{bot}}]^{\top}, \quad \mathbf{u}_{\text{TES}} = [PV_{u,\text{discharge}}, T_{u,\text{TES,in}}]^{\top},$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{GHX}} = [\dot{m}_{\text{GHX,bp}}, Q_{\text{GHX}}]^{\top}, \quad \mathbf{u}_{\text{GHX}} = [\dot{m}_{u,\text{chiller}}, T_{u,\text{chiller,out}}, T_{u,\text{chiller,in}}]^{\top}.$$

These equations are linear in state and input. The entries of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are the learned SINDyC coefficients. \mathbf{d}_{TES} and \mathbf{d}_{GHX} are learned constant offset vectors, that capture steady-state unmodeled effects and sensor biases. To quantify surrogate uncertainty, we adopted a probabilistic aggregation: after fitting many linear SINDyC models, we collected and stacked their coefficient vectors and fit a multivariate Gaussian over them, yielding a single MvG-SINDyC model that provided predictive means and covariances for use in the MPC loop [5].

3.2. Active learning framework

Figure 2. AL pipeline for probabilistic surrogate model construction.

Figure 2 illustrates the AL process used to build the probabilistic surrogate. From the available Modelica trajectories, we first pre-fit a bank of 500 linear SINDyC models, each trained on a random combination of $n \in \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$ trajectories. Using the IES experiment, we constructed an experimental SINDyC model for the GHX after Savitzky–Golay smoothing and resampling, then extracted its coefficient vectors. The AL loop started with 10 random models out of the total of 500 models; all the remaining models were then ranked based on their proximity to the experimental GHX coefficient vector, using the Mahalanobis distance. At each iteration, we formed the current MvG-SINDyC by taking the mean and covariance of the coefficients of the selected models, evaluated predictions of (\dot{m}, Q) on the experimental trajectory, and logged the root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and 95% predictive interval coverage. By “predictive interval coverage”, we mean the fraction of time samples for which the measured \dot{m} or Q lies inside the model’s pointwise [2.5, 97.5] percentile band of its

predictive distribution (obtained by sampling coefficients from $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$ and simulating the surrogate). Higher coverage (closer to 95%) indicates better uncertainty calibration. We then appended the next batch of 10 closest models from the distance ranking and repeated the process until all 500 pre-fit models were consumed. The probabilistic aggregation (means and covariances) was updated as the selected set grew, concentrating the training on those models that were most consistent with the experiment and improved data efficiency. Although models with smaller distance better match the experimental dynamics, a single closest model cannot characterize uncertainty; instead, selecting a set of nearby models balances fidelity with sufficient parameter-space diversity to yield a well-conditioned covariance. As higher-distance models are added, their marginal contribution diminishes and may inflate uncertainty without improving predictive accuracy, naturally defining a practical cutoff.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Mass flow rate \dot{m}

Figure 3. Prediction error trends (RMSE/MAE) for *mass flow* \dot{m} under models trained on different numbers of trajectories.

Figure 3 reports the RMSE and MAE of the mass flow rate \dot{m} for models trained on combinations of (a) 4, (b) 8, (c) 12, and (d) 16 trajectories. These figures illustrate how prediction error evolves as additional SINDyC models are incorporated into the probabilistic surrogate, comparing active learning against random selection across different training-pool sizes. Both strategies began from the same random warm start. We then compared how each strategy evolved from that starting point onward. Across

Figure 4. Prediction error trends (RMSE/MAE) for *power output* Q under models trained on different numbers of trajectories.

pool sizes, AL descends more quickly and settles to a lower plateau than does the Random baseline. In the most data-limited case (4 trajectories), AL shows a clear early drop and attains its best MAE of 0.231 and RMSE of 0.273 at ~ 170 cumulative models, whereas Random improves slowly, with an eventual best MAE of 0.244 at ~ 460 models and an RMSE that remains higher (near ~ 0.28). As the pools grow to 8–16 trajectories, both strategies benefit, but AL maintains a small, persistent edge and reaches its plateau earlier, indicating better sampling efficiency. Mild late-iteration upticks (e.g., beyond $\sim 200 - 300$ selections) reflect high-distance additions with damaging information, suggesting a practical early stopping criterion based on marginal error reduction or query distance.

4.2. Power output Q

Figure 4 shows the RMSE/MAE for the power output Q under the same pool sizes. These figures illustrate how prediction error evolves as additional SINDyC models are incorporated into the probabilistic surrogate, comparing active learning against random selection across different training-pool sizes. Starting from the common warm start, AL again drops faster and stabilizes earlier than does Random. In the 4-trajectory case, AL achieves its best MAE (109.943) by ~ 60 models and its best RMSE (127.474) early in the loop. By contrast, Random attains higher minima later—MAE of 110.334 at ~ 200 models and RMSE of 128.933 at ~ 440 models—indicating slower, weaker improvement. For 8–16 trajectories, both strategies improve with additional data, yet AL sustains lower best-case errors and an earlier plateau. Small late-stage reversals appear when added batches are high distance but low

Figure 5. Combined accuracy-coverage trade-off for AL vs. Random sampling across pool sizes.

information, thus reinforcing the aforementioned possibility of an early stopping criterion.

Figure 5 summarizes the joint trade-off between accuracy and uncertainty calibration as models are added, highlighting how active learning balances error reduction and predictive coverage more efficiently than random sampling. It plots coverage on the x-axis—the percent of the experimental trajectory inside the model’s 95% predictive interval (higher is better)—against normalized RMSE on the y-axis (lower is better), the ideal region being the bottom-right. At each selection step t , we aggregated the two outputs (\hat{m} and Q) into a single accuracy and single coverage measure. We took an equal-weight average of the output-specific RMSEs and the coverages so as to obtain a single combined error and single combined coverage for that step. The AL evaluations trace a Pareto front (red) that lies consistently below and to the right of the Random front (orange), with the clearest separation being for 4–8 trajectories, indicating a superior error-coverage trade-off.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated a data-efficient path to an uncertainty-aware, physics-informed digital twin for TEDS by coupling a probabilistic surrogate (MvG-SINDyC) with an AL selection policy. Starting from a pool of pre-fit models trained on Modelica trajectories, the AL procedure ranked candidate models by utilizing the Mahalanobis distance. At each iteration, we selected the 10 closest candidates, added them to the selected set, refit the MvG-SINDyC surrogate, and then repeated the process. Across the different pool sizes, for both outputs (\hat{m} and Q), the proposed approach consistently achieved faster error reduc-

tion, earlier convergence, and higher best-case coverage than did random sampling, with the largest gains being observed in the low-data regime. As selection proceeded, occasionally-observed late-stage upticks indicated diminishing returns from high-distance additions, suggesting an early stopping criterion based on marginal error decrease and/or query distance thresholds. Future work will focus on comparing this AL framework with other query metrics against alternatives in which the surrogate models are machine-learning-based (e.g., neural networks). Although these models are generally less interpretable than SINDyC, they may offer improved predictive accuracy and overall performance.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. L. Frick, S. M. Bragg-Sitton, and C. Rabiti. "Development of the inl thermal energy distribution system (teds) in the modelica eco-system for validation and verification." Technical report, Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States) (2020).
- [2] L. Lin. "Development of Supervisory Control System for Thermal Energy Distribution System." In *2024 Pacific Basin Nuclear Conference, PBNC 2024*, pp. 435–444. American Nuclear Society (2024).
- [3] L. Lin, J. Oncken, and V. Agarwal. "Autonomous control for Heat-Pipe microreactor using Data-Driven model predictive control." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 200**, p. 110399 (2024).
- [4] B. Kouvaritakis and M. Cannon. "Model predictive control." *Switzerland: Springer International Publishing*, **volume 38**(13-56), p. 7 (2016).
- [5] P. Seurin and L. Lin. "Uncertainty quantification of a physics-informed model based on sparse identification of a Thermal Energy Distribution System." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 226**, p. 111865 (2026).
- [6] K. L. Frick, S. M. Bragg-Sitton, and M. Garrouste. "Validation and Verification for INL Modelica-based TEDS models Via Experimental Results." Technical report, Idaho National Lab.(INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States) (2021).
- [7] S. L. Brunton, J. L. Proctor, and J. N. Kutz. "Discovering governing equations from data by sparse identification of nonlinear dynamical systems." *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, **volume 113**(15), pp. 3932–3937 (2016).
- [8] S. L. Brunton, J. L. Proctor, and J. N. Kutz. "Sparse identification of nonlinear dynamics with control (SINDyC)." *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, **volume 49**(18), pp. 710–715 (2016).
- [9] E. Kaiser, J. N. Kutz, and S. L. Brunton. "Sparse identification of nonlinear dynamics for model predictive control in the low-data limit." *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, **volume 474**(2219), p. 20180335 (2018).
- [10] P. Ren, Y. Xiao, X. Chang, P.-Y. Huang, Z. Li, B. B. Gupta, X. Chen, and X. Wang. "A survey of deep active learning." *ACM computing surveys (CSUR)*, **volume 54**(9), pp. 1–40 (2021).
- [11] H. Ghorbani. "Mahalanobis distance and its application for detecting multivariate outliers." *Facta Universitatis, Series: Mathematics and Informatics*, pp. 583–595 (2019).